

Study of Ag Loaded TiO₂/ZnO Nanocomposites for Photocatalytic Activity

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.19755813

Abstract:

In this research work we reported preparation of TiO₂-ZnO and Ag loaded TiO₂-ZnO nanoparticles with various Ag content via a controlled and an energy efficient microwave assisted method. The structure and properties of photocatalysts were characterized by XRD, SEM and TEM. The crystallite size was found to be 14 nm. The obtained nanomaterials are pseudo-cube in shape. These results are better than pristine TiO₂. The present research work is mainly focused on the enhancement of degradation efficiency of methyl orange (MO) using UV light (365nm). A 94% photodegradation efficiency of MO was achieved by utilizing optimal photocatalysts (Ag-TiO₂-ZnO (0.5 wt% Ag)) at 1 g/dm³ at within 90 min.

Keywords: Spectroscopy, Microwave, Methyl Orange, Degradation.

Introduction:

In the modern era, the nanoscience and nanotechnology are considered to be most emerging in the field of research. Nanomaterials is an ideal for novel applications in a large area including semiconductor [1] gas sensor [2], antimicrobial activity [3], photocatalytic degradation of dyes [4], and hydrogen generation [5]. In 1972, Fujishima and Honda discovered the photocatalytic splitting of water on TiO₂ electrodes [6]. This incident marked the beginning of a new era in heterogeneous photocatalysis. TiO₂ has been the most popular photocatalyst for environmental purification due to its good chemical stability, high oxidized activity, nontoxicity, and low price [7-9]. The photocatalytic process using TiO₂ photocatalyst is very promising for application in the water purification, because many organic compounds can be decomposed and mineralized by the proceeding oxidation and reduction processes on TiO₂ surface [10].

The TiO₂ as a photocatalysts and his effectiveness is sometimes limited due to its wide

band gap (3.2eV) as well as its large charge carrier recombination rate (nanosecond) [11, 12]. Therefore, it is important to develop a novel catalyst which holds high potential for photocatalytic activity. The modification of TiO₂ by coupling with other metal oxides (e.g., WO₃, ZnO, NiO or CoO) is an approach that has received much attention for improving the photocatalytic properties of TiO₂ and that has been considered as an efficient route to increase the lifetime of the charge carrier and tune the band gap to a preferred level [13,14]. Photocatalytic oxidation represents an attractive clarification due to the ability to completely oxidize organic contaminants to carbon dioxide, water, and mineral acids [15]. The absorption of photons with an energy equivalent to or higher than the TiO₂ semiconductor bandgap (E_g) gives rise to photoexcited electron-hole pairs. Electron-hole pairs can begin redox reactions with adsorbates at the catalyst surface or can result in their recombination with the release of heat [16]. In the present work, we have prepared TiO₂-ZnO nanocomposites and further loaded

with Ag, synthesized by a simple microwave assisted method. Its photocatalytic activities were also evaluated by using methyl orange as a model organic compound.

Experimental:

1. Materials:

The 99% purity of Titanium tetra-isopropoxide (TTIP), Zinc nitrate (99%), 99% purity of surfactant cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB), Sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS, 99%) were purchased from Spectrochem Pvt. Ltd., (India). Absolute ethanol (99.9%) and silver nitrate were purchased from s.d. fine chemicals. Ammonia was purchased from Loba Chemie Pvt. Ltd., (India). All analytical grade chemicals were used as received for preparation of various solutions. All solutions were prepared in millipore water obtained from millipore water system (Bangalore, India).

1.1 Preparation of TiO₂-ZnO nanomaterials:

The TiO₂-ZnO nanocomposites were prepared by the simple microwave assisted method using Titanium tetra-isopropoxide, Zinc nitrate, as a source of titanium and zinc. TiO₂-ZnO nanocomposites were prepared by controlled addition of (0.1 M) TTIP in 100 mL of absolute ethanol with constant stirring to get a clear solution. Further, a sufficient amount of surfactant solution (1% CTAB + 1% SDS) was added with constant stirring. For mixed oxides with ZnO, the zinc nitrate solution was varied from 1, 3, and 5 wt%. The required amount of zinc nitrate solution was added to get the desired composition. A solution of aqueous ammonia was added dropwise under stirring condition. With special arrangement at room temperature until the solution reached up to pH=8. After complete precipitation, the precipitate was washed with millipore water and acetone for several times to ensure complete removal of impurities present in sample. The washed precipitate was subjected to

microwave irradiation for 20 min. in a domestic microwave oven (Input 900W, 250 MHz, LG Make) with on-off cycle (20s on-40s off). The dried powder was grounded by using agate mortar and pestle and calcined at 300°C for 3 hrs in a temperature controlled muffle furnace. These prepared samples such as TiO₂, TiO₂-ZnO (1, 3, and 5 wt. % ZnO) and ZnO were denoted as T, TZ1, TZ2, TZ3, and Z respectively.

1.2 Preparation of Ag loaded TiO₂-ZnO nanocomposites:

The Ag loaded TiO₂-ZnO were prepared by above simple microwave assisted method was further modified with silver nanoparticles (NPs) using impregnation-reduction method. Synthesized TiO₂-ZnO powder having optimum content of ZnO (3 wt% of ZnO) was added in 20 mL millipore water and sonicated for 30 min for in order to achieve proper dispersion. For synthesis of different wt% Ag (0.25 to 1.0) loading, calculated amount of silver nitrate was added in above mixture and then stirred for 60 min. so as to form proper solution between Ag⁺ and TiO₂-ZnO. Reduction of Ag⁺ was achieved by using calculated amount of freshly prepared ice cold solution of Sodium Borohydride. The prepared Ag loaded TiO₂-ZnO nanocomposites powder was dried at 110°C for 60 min to remove water content and denoted as TZ-Ag1 to TZ-Ag4 for different Ag content (0.25 to 1.0 wt % Ag) respectively.

2. Photocatalytic activity of TiO₂-ZnO and Ag-TiO₂-ZnO nanocomposites:

The photocatalytic activity of TiO₂-ZnO and Ag loaded TiO₂-ZnO was evaluated by testing the degradation of methyl orange as a model pollutant by using UV light (365 nm). To search the highest photocatalytic activity of mixed oxides, catalyst amount was varied from 0.75 to 1.5 g/dm³. The quartz photoreactor was kept in steel container along with magnetic

stirrer. Philips (HPL-N, 250 W) light source was used which has Lumens of 12750. Outer side of the bulb was broken and just inside filament is used as a source of light. The distance of lamp was kept 5 cm above the dye solution. In the given experiment the photocatalyst was added in photoreactor containing methyl orange (100 mL, 20 ppm). Prior to irradiation, dye solution was stirred for 30 minutes in dark for adsorption-desorption equilibrium. All photodegradation experiments were performed at ambient temperature. At a given time interval, samples were withdrawn and centrifuged to remove photocatalyst. The absorbance of the clear solution was recorded by using UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Model-UV-3600) to monitor the concentration of dye.

Results and Discussion:

1. Characterization of as prepared TiO₂-ZnO and Ag-TiO₂-ZnO nanocomposites:

1.1. XRD:

The modification mechanism is closely related to the crystallite structure, which has been studied using the XRD technique. Fig. 1(a) shows the X-ray diffraction patterns of variable TiO₂/ZnO composites with pristine TiO₂ and ZnO. In Fig. 1(a), the sample 'T' determined characteristics 2θ values and [hkl] planes are 25.06° [101], 37.59° [004], 48.01° [200], 55.02° [211], 62.31° [204] attributed to reflections of anatase TiO₂ which is compared with JCPD Card No. (21-1272) [17]. For the sample 'Z' determined characteristics 2θ values and [hkl] planes, all the diffraction peaks are observed at 31.82° [100], 34.47° [002], 36.34° [101], 47.69° [102], 56.63° [110], 62.91° [103] and 67.93° [112] which can be well indexed as a hexagonal wurtzite structure and consistent with the values of standard data (JCPDS 36-1451) [18].

Meanwhile, for the sample TZ1, TZ2 and TZ3 the peaks of ZnO were not observed in the XRD pattern due to low content of Zn. Almost all diffraction peaks of the samples can be indexed to the anatase TiO₂ indicating that Zn²⁺ were dissolved into the TiO₂ host lattice without disturbing the crystal structure of TiO₂. The possibility of substitution of Zn²⁺ is ruled out due to difference in ionic radii Ti⁴⁺=0.61 and Zn²⁺=0.74pm. The average crystallite size of samples T, TZ1, TZ2, TZ3 and Z was calculated by using Scherrer's relation:

$$t = 0.9\lambda/\beta \cos \theta \quad \text{----- (1)}$$

Where λ is wavelength of X-ray in Å, β is full width at half maximum [FWHM] in radian. θ is scattering angle in degree. The relatively broad width of peaks of the XRD patterns implies crystallites are smaller in size [19]. At 300°C the average crystallite size for sample T was found to be about 15 nm, As the Zn contents increase from 1 to 5 wt %, the broadening of the peak [101] gradually increases which indicates the smaller crystallite size of the material. It is observed that the 'T' has an average size of 15 nm and it decreases up to 12 nm for TZ2. The Z sample has average crystallite size of 25 nm.

Fig. 1(b) shows the X-ray diffraction patterns of different wt % Ag loaded on TiO₂-ZnO. The diffraction pattern of all samples (TZ-Ag1 to TZ-Ag4) reveals that there is formation of crystalline structure with anatase phase. Although the Ag content was increased from 0.25 to 1.0 wt% the crystalline structures of the mixed oxides were still the anatase TiO₂. Hence, the loading of Ag at such low contents did not significantly affect the crystalline structure. Major peak for TiO₂-ZnO found to be almost same for Ag loaded TiO₂-ZnO mixed oxide samples, except changes in intensity of peaks. It is observed that for TZ2 nanomaterial crystallite size was found to be 12 nm and it increases upto 14 nm for 0.5 wt% Ag

on TZ2, thereafter the crystallite size of the photocatalyst was more or less constant. The appearance of Ag metallic peak is not observed in the XRD pattern of nanocomposites this is may be due to the low Ag content and also high dispersion of Ag nanoparticles on the surface of the $\text{TiO}_2\text{-ZnO}$.

Fig. 1(a). X-ray diffractograms of a) TiO_2 (T) b) TiO_2/ZnO (1 wt% ZnO-TZ1) c) TiO_2/ZnO (3 wt% ZnO-TZ2) d) TiO_2/ZnO (5 wt% ZnO-TZ3) e) ZnO (Z) nanoparticles

Fig. 1(b). X-Ray diffraction pattern of a) TiO_2 (T) b) TiO_2/ZnO (3 wt% ZnO-TZ2) c) Ag- TiO_2/ZnO (0.5 Wt% Ag) d) ZnO (Z)

1.2 SEM and EDS analysis of $\text{TiO}_2\text{-ZnO}$ and Ag- $\text{TiO}_2\text{-ZnO}$:

In order to investigate the surface morphology of the synthesized TZ2 and TZ-Ag2 nanoparticles, SEM and elemental composition studies were performed. The particles of TZ2 and TZ-Ag2 have pseudo-cube like morphology which is shown in Fig. 2A(a) and 2B(a). The SEM images of prepared TZ-Ag2 compared with TZ2, confirmed that the TZ-Ag2 shows smaller particle size than TZ2. The EDS instrument also show coloured photographic image for specific element depending upon composition present in area under study. EDS mapping of $\text{TiO}_2\text{-ZnO}$ and Ag- $\text{TiO}_2\text{-ZnO}$ were shown in Fig. 2A(b) and 2B(b). Fig. 2A(c) and 2B(c) shows EDS spectrum of as synthesized TZ2 and TZ-Ag2 nanoparticles. The EDS was recorded in the binding energy region of 0-10 keV. The findings of all EDS confirms presence of Ti, O, Zn and Ag elements in synthesized materials as well as revealing amount of Ag loading. The peak from the spectrum revealed the presence of Ti, O, Zn and Ag at 4.48, 0.50, 0.98, and 0.25 keV respectively. EDS mapping indicates that almost all samples formed were of non-stoichiometry TiO_2 with oxygen deficient which leads to better performance of photocatalytic activity [20].

Fig.2 (A). SEM and EDS analysis of TZ2 (3 wt% ZnO)

Fig.2 (B). SEM and EDS analysis of TZ-Ag₂ (0.5 Wt% Ag)

1.3. TEM Result:

Morphology of the nanomaterials was characterized by TEM analysis as shown in Fig. 3(a). The obtained image reveals that as prepared TZ2 is in the form of pseudo-cube with narrow size distribution. The size of particles is in the range of 12-15 nm, with the average particle size from representative TEM was found to be 12 nm. The HR-TEM image (Fig.3b) shows lattice fringes, which is used for phase identification and found to be 0.35 nm. The value corresponds to the lattice spacing of (101) plane in the anatase phase. Selected area electron diffraction pattern (SAED) matches to anatase phase with good crystallinity as shown in Fig. 3(c). Lattice fringes can be clearly indicating that the particles are crystalline with anatase phase.

Fig. 3. TEM Image of a) TZ2 (3 wt% ZnO) Nanoparticles b) HRTEM image of TZ2 (3 wt% ZnO) c) SAED Pattern of TZ2 (3 wt% ZnO)

2. Factors affecting photocatalytic degradation of methyl orange:

2.1 Effect of concentration of ZnO (wt %) on TiO₂ for MO degradation:

Fig. 4(a) shows the photocatalytic degradation of methyl orange on TiO₂-ZnO photocatalyst with varying ZnO concentrations of 1, 3 and 5 wt % of ZnO. From figure it can be concluded that, all the composite samples (TZ1, TZ2 and TZ3) shows better degradation efficiency of Methyl orange (MO) as compared to

pristine TiO₂ and ZnO. More importantly, due to the presence of a TiO₂-ZnO composite, recombination of the photogenerated electron-hole charge carriers were markedly reduced. Additionally, electrons or holes that transfer to the TiO₂ or ZnO active surface of the hybrid nanostructures immediately join in the redox reactions, in which electrons reduce dissolved molecular oxygen to produce superoxide radical anions (O₂⁻), while holes oxidize H₂O molecular to yield hydroxyl radicals

(·OH). Organic dye pollutants (MO) are eventually oxidized by these highly active species to CO_2 and H_2O products [21]. The optimal TZ2 (3 Wt % ZnO) photocatalyst shows maximum 87% degradation of methyl orange within 90 min for 1 g/dm^3 photocatalyst which seems to be good result.

Fig. 4(a). Effect of concentration of ZnO on TiO_2 for MO degradation

2.2 Effect of concentration of Ag (wt %) on TiO_2 -ZnO for MO degradation:

Fig. 4(b) shows the photocatalytic degradation of methyl orange on TZ-Ag photocatalyst with varying Ag concentrations from 0.25 to 1.0 wt % and noted as TZ-Ag1 to TZ-Ag4. From figure it can be concluded that, the TZ-Ag2 photocatalyst shows maximum 94% degradation of methyl orange within 90 min for 1 g/dm^3 photocatalyst which seems to be good result as compared to TZ nanocomposites. It may consider that in TZ-Ag composite, the excited electrons of TiO_2 and ZnO can quickly transfer from the conduction band of TiO_2 or ZnO to Ag, and then effectively suppresses the recombination of photo-generated charge carriers, leaving more charge carriers to form highly reactive species (O_2 , ·OH) and promote the degradation of dye [22].

Fig. 4(b). Effect of concentration of Ag on TiO_2/ZnO for MO degradation

2.3 Effect of Catalyst loading:

Photocatalysis is heterogeneous in nature and its efficiency depends upon concentration of reactant and active sites of the photocatalyst [23]. The effect of catalyst loading on photocatalytic degradation of methyl orange (20 ppm) has been examined under UV light. Therefore, the amounts of catalyst were varied from 0.75 to 1.5 g/dm^3 by keeping other parameters identical. Fig. 5 shows that increase in catalyst loading from 0.75 to 1 g/dm^3 increases the degradation efficiency from 72% to 94% within 90 min. A maximum 94% degradation of methyl orange was obtained at 1.0 g/dm^3 under UV light within 90 min. The degradation efficiency increases with the increase in amount of catalyst loading up to 1.0 g/dm^3 , which is attributed to the increase in the number of active sites and the number of photon absorbed by catalyst are more favorable for photocatalysis. Further increase in the catalyst loading, a decrease in degradation efficiency up to 68% was observed. This observation can be explained in terms of large amount of catalyst may result in the agglomeration of the catalyst. This decreases the number of active sites [24].

Fig. 5. Effect of catalyst loading on methyl orange degradation

Conclusions:

In summary, TiO₂-ZnO and Ag loaded TiO₂-ZnO nanoparticles with different Ag content have been synthesized by using a simple, ecofriendly, energy efficient and cost effective microwave assisted method. It was observed that for TZ2 nanomaterial, crystallite size was found to be 12 nm and it increases upto 14 nm for 0.5 wt% Ag on TZ2, thereafter the crystallite size of the photocatalyst was more or less constant. The obtained nanomaterials are pseudo-cube in shape. A 94% degradation of MO was achieved by utilizing 0.5 wt % Ag loaded TZ2 (1 g/dm³) photocatalyst within 90 min. under UV- light irradiation. These results are better than pristine TiO₂.

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